

Organisational Evidence Assessment

- User Manual -

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1. Introduction

The *Assessment and Management of Organisational Evidence* component (a.k.a. *AMOE*) enables Cloud Service Providers (CSP) to generate assessment results for the continuous auditing of their security policy documents.

AMOE allows a compliance manager or an auditor to upload a policy document and view extracted evidence parts of the document relevant for MEDINA security metrics. The application can provide pre-assessment results, requiring the user only to inspect, confirm or edit and submit the final assessment result to the MEDINA framework. The main parts of *AMOE* are summarized in the following:

- Upload a policy document. The application processes the document and extracts evidence, and generates pre-assessment hints based on the metrics of the *Catalogue of Controls and Metrics*¹ and their respective configurations (e.g., Target Values) stored in the *Orchestrator*².
- View extracted assessment results.
- Set/Change assessment results.
- Submit assessment results.
- Delete all the data uploaded and stored directly in the component (except log data).

1.1. User Roles and Permissions

Access to *AMOE* is managed by Keycloak³. The visibility of the different elements of the *AMOE* UI, and the operations that are allowed to be carried out, are conditioned by the role to which each user is assigned. The main permissions are the following:

- **Read entities:** Read everything in *AMOE* that the user is allowed to (linked to a cloud service configured for the user).
- **Upload and delete entities:** Upload files and delete all data in *AMOE*.
- **Edit:** Edit assessment status of results, edit comments, and submit assessment results to the *Orchestrator*.

The table below details which actions are allowed for each of the defined roles:

Roles	Allowed Actions
IT Security Governance	Read entities
Security Analyst	Read entities
Domain Governance	Read entities
Product and Service Owner	Read entities
Product (Security) Engineer	Read entities, Upload and delete entities
Chief Information Security Office (CISO)	Read entities
Customer	None
Auditor	Read entities, edit assessment results, add comments, submit assessment results

¹ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D2.2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7794478>

² For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D3.6 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927225>

³ <https://www.keycloak.org>

2. User Manual

2.1. Toolbar

AMOE includes a toolbar (see Figure 1), always accessible in the upper area. The *Uploaded files* button provides access to the list of files that have been uploaded to AMOE. The *Help* button provides access the user manual.

Figure 1. AMOE toolbar

2.2. Uploaded files

The *Uploaded files* view is the main view of AMOE (see Figure 2). It first presents an overview of existing uploaded policy files and the possibility to upload a new one.

Process organisational evidence based on metrics

Uploaded files

Uploaded files Upload new file

Show 50 entries Search:

Cloud service	File name	Date	Progress	Delete
Fabasoft Cloud Service	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf	2023-07-24 10:51:46	100.0%	Delete
Fabasoft Cloud Service	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf	2023-07-24 10:34:16	100.0%	Delete
Fabasoft Cloud Service	UTF-8MEDINA20dummy20policies20Fabasoft20M18.pdf	2023-05-31 10:19:27	100.0%	Delete
Fabasoft Cloud Service	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf	2023-05-24 05:56:04	100.0%	Delete
Fabasoft Cloud Service	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf	2023-05-02 10:12:47	process has been interrupted	Delete
Fabasoft Cloud Service	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf	2023-04-27 12:22:44	100.0%	Delete
Fabasoft Cloud Service	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf	2023-04-27 09:05:57	100.0%	Delete
Fabasoft Cloud Service	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf	2023-04-26 12:23:21	99.35%	Delete
Bosch_IaaS	today_Bosch_IoT_Cloud_Security_Concept.pdf	2023-04-20 12:43:35	90.00%	Delete

Figure 2. AMOE landing page

2.2.1. Upload a policy file

To use the AMOE GUI, start by clicking on the "Upload new file" button. A file upload dialog box will then appear, as shown in Figure 3. This dialog is only available for users with "upload and delete" permissions (see section 1.1).

Upload new file

Upload a policy PDF file for AMOE to scan for organisational evidence. The file is processed in the background and extracts evidence for every security metric in the MEDINA catalogue.

Need authorization?

Select cloud service

FabasoftTestCCD

Figure 3. AMOE file upload dialog

Select a policy PDF document to upload, or enter a URL from where AMOE should download the file. If the file download requires credentials, these can be provided by using the *Need authorization* functionality. Also enter the cloud service (id) to connect to. Then click on *Upload* and the page shown in Figure 4 is displayed.

Process organisational evidence based on metrics

Uploaded files

Success! Upload successful, MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf - 6423f2fa43f1d3ba43577c73

Uploaded files

Show 50 entries Search:

Cloud service	File name	Date	Progress	Delete
CCD Faba TEST	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf	2023-03-29 08:12:42	process is starting	<input type="button" value="Stop"/>
CCD Faba TEST	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf	2023-02-28 15:13:21	100.0%	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>
Bosch_SaaS	AWS_C5_-_DE_Final_Report_-_9_30_2018.pdf	2023-02-21 08:26:22	100.0%	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>
Bosch_PaaS	Microsoft_Azure_Germany_SOC_2_Type_II_Report_10-1-2020_to_9-30-2021.pdf	2023-02-21 08:26:03	100.0%	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>
CCD Faba TEST	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf	2023-02-20 13:57:11		<input type="button" value="Delete"/>
Bosch_IaaS	Bosch_loT_Cloud_Security_Concept.pdf	2023-02-14 14:51:51	100.0%	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>
CCD Faba TEST	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf	2023-02-10 11:06:33	98.51%	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>
CCD Faba TEST	MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v4.pdf	2023-01-10 10:41:43	92.52%	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>
Bosch Cloud Service	Bosch_loT_Cloud_Security_Concept.pdf	2023-01-04 06:51:12	69.40% 30.51%	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>

Figure 4. AMOE landing page after file upload

The evidence extraction process is started in the background. It can take some time until every organisational metric has been processed. The process can be stopped by clicking on the turquoise *Stop* button in Figure 4. Files and their linked evidence can be deleted by clicking on the red *Delete* button.

Figure 5 depicts the progress of the background evidence extraction process. On hovering, the details are shown. Only users with “upload and delete” permission are shown the *Delete* and *Stop* buttons.

The screenshot shows a table with columns for Date, Progress, and Delete. A tooltip is visible over the Progress column, displaying the text: "Metrics are being processed (1/118 - 0.85%)".

Date	Progress	Delete
2023-03-29 08:12:42	<div style="width: 0.85%;"></div>	Stop
2023-02-28 15:13:21	100.0%	Delete

Figure 5. AMOE evidence extraction progress

Figure 6 shows the status overview. This is displayed for every file after the evidence extraction process has finished. The details are shown by hovering with the mouse. Green indicates the number of assessment results set to compliant, red the number set to not compliant, and grey marks where no status has been set (undefined).

Figure 6. AMOE assessment status overview per document

2.2.2. View extracted evidence / assessment results

To view the evidence results of an uploaded file, click on a row of the respective table or the filename of the list, as depicted in Figure 4. The overview, as depicted in Figure 7, opens. This overview contains meta data of the uploaded file, filter, and search options. In case an assessment result has been set, it can be submitted to the *Orchestrator* directly from this view. Otherwise, click on a row to get to the detailed view for the extracted evidence.

Users with “edit” permission can use the *Submit* functionality from this page if the assessment status has been already set and the entry has not been submitted yet. Multiple assessment results can be sent at once if selected using the checkbox and clicking on the *Send multi assessment results* button.

Help

View evidence

Uploaded files / MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf

Information about the file

Cloud service: FabasoftTestCCD
 File id: 63e5fd22e09529afe53309c0
 File name: MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf
 Uploaded on: 2023-02-10 08:15:30 by ccd_admin
 Extracted evidence count: 118 / 118

Filter CAB assessment

Compliant: 10 / 11

Not compliant: 1

Undefined: 104 / 118 (88.14%)

[Reset filter](#)

Extracted evidence [Send multi assessment results](#)

Show 50 entries Search:

<input type="checkbox"/>	MetricID	Question	Answer	AMOE assessment hint	CAB assessment	Submitted to Orchestrator
<input type="checkbox"/>	PasswordPolicyQ1	Which parameters define the password policy?	Passwords should have at least 10 upper -and lowercase characters and contain numbers as well as special characters . Do not reuse passwords for multiple services. Passwords should not be	Undefined	✓ True	✓ Submitted
<input type="checkbox"/>	PasswordPolicyQ2	What is the passwords maximum age according to the password policy?	encrypted passwords. The password needs to be changed after a maximum time duration of 60 days .	✓ True	✓ True	Submit
<input type="checkbox"/>	PasswordPolicyQ3	What is the passwords rotation frequency?	Passwords should have at least 10 upper -and lowercase characters and contain numbers as well	✗ False	✗ False	Please add a comment to submit
<input type="checkbox"/>	PasswordPolicyQ4	Which requirements exist for password managers?	best practice to use password managers to generate complex passwords and store the encrypted passwords . The password needs to be changed after a maximum time duration of 60	Undefined	Undefined	Please set CAB assessment status

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries (filtered from 118 total entries) Previous 1 Next

Figure 7. AMOE overview of extracted evidence and meta data linked to the uploaded file

2.2.3. View compliance status / assessment result details

Figure 8 depicts the detailed view of the extracted evidence. The linked requirement is shown on the top. This is followed by the metric meta data, extracted answer, assessment hint and options to set the assessment result and comment. Only users with “edit” permission can change the assessment status and comment and submit the results to the *Orchestrator*.

The screenshot displays the 'View compliance status' page. At the top, it shows the breadcrumb 'Uploaded files / MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf / PasswordPolicyQ2'. Below this, it lists 'EUCS Requirement(s) linked to Metric' with a header 'IAM-08 - PROTECTION AND STRENGTH OF CREDENTIALS'. The requirement details include: Requirement id: IAM-08.1H; Requirement description: 'The CSP shall document, communicate and make available to all users under its responsibility rules and recommendations for the management of credentials, including at least: (1) Non-reuse of credentials; (2) Trade-offs between entropy and ability to memorize; (3) Recommendations for renewal of passwords; (4) Rules on storage of passwords. (5) Recommendations on password managers (6) Recommendation to specifically address classical attacks, including phishing, social attacks, and whaling'; Requirement assurance level: High; Requirement type: ORGANIZATIONAL.

The 'Metric - PasswordPolicyQ2' section is divided into two columns. The left column contains: Keywords: password, age, maximum; Target value: <= 90.0 (Integer); Question: 'What is the passwords maximum age according to the password policy?'; Answer: 'encrypted passwords. The password needs to be changed after a maximum time duration of 60 days .'. The right column contains: File id: 63e5fd22e09529afe53309c0; File name: MEDINA_dummy_policies_Fabasoft_M18v5.pdf; Extraction date: 2023-02-10 08:37:07. There are buttons for 'Show processed' and 'Show original'.

The 'Assessment' section shows: Assessment hint: 'compliant (60 days <= 90.0 (Integer))'; Assessment status: 'compliant' (with a dropdown arrow and a lightning bolt icon for 'not compliant'); Last change on: 2023-03-29 08:20:52 by admin; Compliance comment: A text area with the placeholder 'Please enter a comment regarding the assessment status.' and a note 'The comment has not been changed yet'. A 'Submit to orchestrator' button is present with the message 'No submission yet.' At the bottom, there are navigation buttons for 'previous metric', '84/118', and 'next metric'.

Figure 8. AMOE view of organisational evidence

2.2.4. View extracted evidence in HTML

Figure 9 shows the processed HTML version of the document. The extracted evidence is highlighted in green.

Figure 9. Show processed evidence (HTML view)

2.3. API

The OpenAPI file can be downloaded by accessing <host>/openapi.json

Figure 10 shows the list of available endpoints. The request must include a valid keycloak token issued from the MEDINA setup.

GET	/api/v1/files/{cloud_service_id}	AMOE List Files Cloud Sevice	∨
POST	/api/v1/files/	AMOE List Files Cloud Sevices	∨
GET	/api/v1/file/{file_id}	AMOE Get File	∨
GET	/api/v1/file/last/{cloud_service_id}	get_amoee_last_file	∨
GET	/api/v1/evidence/list/{file_id}	AMOE Get List Evidence For File	∨
POST	/api/v1/evidence/list_per_metric_id	AMOE Get List Evidence Per Metric	∨
GET	/api/v1/evidence/{evidence_id}	AMOE Get Evidence	∨
POST	/api/v1/evidence/assessment	AMOE Set Assessment Result	∨
GET	/api/v1/evidence/send_to_orchestrator/{evidence_id}	AMOE Send Assessment Result	∨
GET	/api/v1/evidence/file/{evidence_id}	AMOE Get HTML File	∨
GET	/api/v1/file/pdf/{file_id}	AMOE Get PDF File	∨
POST	/api/v1/file/{cloud_service}	AMOE Upload PDF File	∨
GET	/api/v1/file/delete/{file_id}	AMOE Delete File And Evidence	∨

Figure 10. AMOE API

3. Delivery and Usage

3.1. Licensing information

This component is offered under Apache 2.0 license. The license files and more detailed information can be found in the MEDINA Public GitLab repository⁴.

3.2. Download

The code of the component is available at the public GitLab repository of the MEDINA project:

<https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/AMOE>

3.3. More information

Interested readers can find more information about *AMOE* in the following links:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927225> “D3.6 Tools and techniques for collecting evidence of technical and organisational measures – v3”

The MEDINA web site (<https://medina-project.eu/>) also includes several deliverables related to *AMOE*.

⁴ <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/AMOE>